

From makers to circular communities. A tool for sustainable emancipation

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Abstract

The paper describes the output of a PhD research project focused on opportunities of sustainability in the maker world. The project arises from the need to achieve a sustainable emancipation at all levels of designing, from the engineering and the industrial design to the level of do-it-yourself people, thanks to the creation of new dedicated tools. DIY-people are seen as accelerators of the transition to a sustainable society, in particular they play the role of intermediary between technical actors of production supply and consumers.

Moreover it was found that Life Cycle Assessment is the most relevant methodology for environmental impact calculation, by the way the software and DB used for it are complex and mostly private and expensive.

Consequently the main goal has been to make sustainability tools and methods accessible to non-technical people involved in making, in order to disseminate the Life Cycle Thinking.

The output of the research is a collaborative mobile App, where an Easy LCA tool has been developed to increase the green expertise of the users, and generate a local and circular community .

The project has seen the collaboration between the Department of Architecture and Design of University of Florence and the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering of Delft University of Technology.

Keywords

Sustainability, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) , Collaborative Platforms, DIY, Prosumers

1 Background

The project arises from the need to achieve a sustainable emancipation at all levels of designing, from the engineering and the industrial design level to do-it-yourself people, through the creation of dedicated tools.

The starting assumption is the sprouting of a new critical making, that shows a renewing interest in sociocultural histories as well as environmental and economical implication, as the emerging of initiatives of local communal electronics depot, repair and upcycling communities, and research and educational platforms centering around sustainable materials and open-source tools (L.Bogers, L.Chiappini 2019).

Moreover the project refers to a critical design line that starting from '70 is proposing to give back an active role to consumers, sharing with them knowledge through do-it-yourself solutions, with the idea to break the actual industrial supply chain.

Under all there is the denounced, first by Victor Papanek and just later by Enzo Mari, against the attitude of design to respond no longer to necessary needs but to superfluous needs accessible to a few, thus forgetting their social role of meeting the needs of the many.

Papanek, along with James Hennessey, released *Nomadic Furniture* in 1973, the book with diagrams of DIY plans, shared with readers "How to build and where to buy lightweight furniture that folds, inflates, knocks down, stacks, or is disposable and can be recycled,"-

Further *Autoprogettazione* (1974) wants to be a democratization act, Enzo Mari putting his expertise as a designer at the disposal of many, and proposes a small guide with easy-to-build open source projects.

He takes sides in aid of consumers and in contrast with a selective manufacturing system, it enables consumers to play an active role in the production chain. The guide meets the people's need to furnish one's home at moderate costs, and at the same time creates quite a stir as it seems to deliver to users the knowledge and means to become independent from the manufactured goods market, at the risk of handing over the secrets of the trade and going bankrupt.

Mari gives back to man the possibility of returning at least in part to a craftsman, with the freedom to actually respond to his own needs, today one would say in a customized way.

Therefore from the denunciation of the designer's social responsibility, emerges the responsibility to intercept and propose the transformations necessary for society. And in this regard is placed the present research, directing today the responsibility of designs in encouraging change towards a sustainable society.

Today the exhibition *NOMADIC FURNITURE 3.0. New Liberated Living?* design by raumlaborberlin the Vienna's MAK, in 2013 presents DIY movement from its nascence to the present Web 2.0 culture, examines this movement situated on the threshold between the subcultural and the mainstream including a look at its historical context.

Over the past decade, the new opportunities of communication and participation represented by the Internet and Web 2.0 have taken DIY-cultural hype to a renewed fever-pitch. DIY portals, communities, and blogs are booming, and designers, programmers, constructors of machines, and users are busy developing new Internet-capable modalities of designing and producing furniture and furnishing items.

What we are witnessing today is a new democratization of knowledge, what at first were simple technological innovations spreading more and more among non-technical people, bringing social innovation. Desktop manufacturing systems, combined with the internet network, are changing the way of producing and above all the relationships between producers, suppliers and consumers (Anderson).

The Italian group *Recession Design*, born in Milan in 2008, is made up of professionals who share a critical vision on the world of contemporary design, and use the pretext of the 2008 economic crisis to open a debate on what it means to "design" today. *The publication Recession design. New ideas against the crisis. DIY design 2.0* launch a provocation towards a self-celebratory design in favor of a new design model presented as an alternative to the designer-producer-customer chain, in which the elimination of the traditional production and distribution phase is put into practice, thanks to the possibility of transfer to design the new methods of sharing knowledge, typical of social networks and the open source web philosophy.

Moreover Ezio Manzini in *Design when everybody designs* (2015) challenges us all to rethink the role of design and that of the 'designers' in contemporary society. "The role of design, both expert and nonexpert, in the ongoing wave of social innovation toward sustainability." He wants us to reimagine design's relationship to addressing social innovation and building a sustainable and resilient culture.

He maps what design experts can do to trigger and support meaningful social changes, focusing on emerging forms of collaboration.

These range from community-supported agriculture in China to digital platforms for medical care in Canada; from interactive storytelling in India to collaborative housing in Milan. These cases illustrate how expert designers can support these collaborations—making their existence more probable, their practice easier, their diffusion and their convergence in larger projects more effective.

Manzini draws the first comprehensive picture of design for social innovation: the most dynamic field of action for both expert and nonexpert designers in the coming decades.

What has changed is people's attitude, they have become more conscious of alternative and sustainable solutions due to the failing system of the current paradigm. At the same time, technologies that can democratize and accelerate innovation have diffused to our everyday life.

Information communication technologies (ICT) have emerged as an enabling solution that facilitates grassroots social innovations. Among them are collaborative services in which the final users collaborate to provide solutions to their unmet social needs. These alternative solutions aggregate to result in radical innovations towards a sustainable society (Meroni ed., 2006).

These two conditions create a favourable condition to diffuse social innovation with an urgent need for designers to participate.

This research discusses issues on design for sustainability and education for sustainability which specializes in service design for social innovation at the grassroots level.

2 DIY-people as accelerators of sustainability (target: prosumers)

As Manzini claims, transition towards sustainability is a social learning process that requires active involvement of social constituents (Manzini in Meroni ed., 2007). The assumption is that as in the past designers have empowered their clients by giving them tools and knowledge to bypass companies, with the advantage of creating something custom and cheap.

Nowadays we ask designers something similar, to empower people with sustainable knowledge.

To achieve this the research focused on a specific target that has been considered ready to receive that knowledge.

In particular DIY-people are seen as accelerators of the transition to a sustainable society, in the way that they play the role of intermediary between technical actors of production supply and consumers.

DIY-people fit with the figure of prosumers, people who produce some of the goods and services entering their own consumption (A.Toffler, 1980), that today is associate with new form of economy based on sharing and collaboration spread with the Millennials generation (N.Radjou, J.Prabhu 2016).

Nowadays multiple tools and methods have been created to achieve the sustainability of a product or their process. Those are structured to help designers in both quantitative and quality evaluation.

The most relevant, thanks to his normalization, is the Life Cycle Assessment methodology.

By the way the software and DB used for this assessment are complex and mostly private and expensive. On the other side we believe that accessibility to tools and knowledge is the key to reach a global development. For this reason the goal of the project has been to make sustainability tools and methods accessible to the prosumer target, so non-technical people involved in making.

3 Research method and result

The research has been developed in three steps. First of all has been verified the relationship between sustainability and DIY/maker movement, through the construction of a common timeline to tracking their development, then mapping the actual ecosystem around these two topics.

Second step has been to verify the tools and methodologies for sustainable design. In particular Life Cycle Assessment has been applied to universities research projects from Design for Sustainability Lab (University of Florence) to assist the redesign of camper and train interior, as well as service system. Then LCA has been applied to DIY projects, to evaluate camper van transformation with a local collective.

Furthermore, a workshop has been created to verify educational opportunities of LCA as a regional training course. Tested both with young professionals of the manufacturing sector and universities students of industrial design and fashion.

The last step has seen the development of a phone app where non-expert users can realize LCA, thanks to the Easy LCA tool, and generate a local network for exchange of materials or knowledge through a collaborative platform system.

4 Discussion: Sustainability & self-production scenario

The timeline shows that while the concept of sustainability has evolved from attention to company's efficiency to a more huge concept where there is now even social innovation, at the same time the answers of design have moved in between critical actions and the development of tools and methods for achieving a sustainable design.

The present research is positioned in this line, with the intention to let an accessible evaluation tool for the impact assessment.

4.1 Mapping of the ecosystem

From the construction of the timeline it has been possible to establish the relationship between the two scenarios of research, sustainable development and self-production.

To verify the opportunity of a project in this intermediate field, the research focuses on the mapping of the stakeholders that are active in this scenario.

So 60 case studies (Table 1) in between companies, designers, associations, foundations, collectives, laboratories, networks, projects, instruments and platforms have been analyzed. For each case a profile sheet has been generated, where a compass rose with a selection of 12 parameters describing the role of the stakeholder in the scenario.

From the map emerged a classification of four roles active in the scenario of sustainability/ self-production: drivers, tools, projects and places (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The 12 parameter and the categories

Drivers: They play the role of internal promoters of the ecosystem. The tools and output categories are often a consequence of their activities. Drivers are guided by a different vision of the future society, and they practice more top-down actions. Addressing their service to entrepreneurs and municipalities

In general the starting assumptions are first of all the need to change the economic-environmental models, from the scale of the manufacturing product to the urban one. Secondly a global emancipation,

so proposing social innovation projects also supported by the tools of environmental sustainability, experiences as urban gardens, or social-local workshops.

Tools: are mostly generated by drivers to complete their actions as accelerators and educators, and could be the results of collaboration between different drivers. In general tools allow spread of expertise and use open channels. Therefore tools enable customers to access new market scenarios and new partnerships. They facilitate the exchange of products and knowledge, facilitating global networks where training and dissemination takes place. They allow the experimentation of alternative market solutions.

Places: are places of aggregation, where it is possible to get in touch with drivers. Result of local and global synergies. Experimentation labs for new market solutions, participation and open design. Place of rediscovery of local resources in terms of human capital, place where promoters bottom-up process.

Projects: Research projects carried out by the drivers. They demonstrate how development strategies are applied to sustainable and social innovation. They often bring together drivers with places and result in the creation of new tools.

1.Driver*	2.Place*	3.Tool*	4.Project*
<p>organization</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. ELLEN MACARTHUR F. 2. METABOLIC 3. P2PFoundation 4. GIG 5. CIRCLE 6. ATLANTE EC <hr/> <p>designers</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 7. OPENDESK 8. SLOWD 9. SDS 10. IDEO.org <hr/> <p>university</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. DESIS NETWORK 12. Institute of Making UCL <hr/> <p>web platform</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13. Faberin 14. Make.Works 15. SFRIDOO 16. RICICLARIO 	<p>global network</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. FABLAB 2. ARTISAN'S ASYLUM <hr/> <p>local</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 3. LOFOIO 4. OPENDOT 5. WEMAKE 6. GALLAB 7. BRICHECO 8. OFFICINE ZERO 9. ESPACIO OPEN 10. GOLDFINGER FACTORY <hr/> <p>companies</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 11. TECHSHOP 12. LOCAL MOTORS 	<p>abilitanti</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CC LICENCE 2. ARDUINO 3. RASPBERRY PI 4. MAKERBOT <hr/> <p>web platform</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. IFIXIT 6. THINGIVERSE 7. POKONO 8. QUIRKY 9. 3HUB 10. SHAPEWAYS 11. REPRAP 12. ETSY <hr/> <p>education</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 13. LENS 14. IDEMAT 15. CIRCULATOR 16. CIRCULAR DESIGN GUIDE 17. SUSTAINABLE DESIGN CARD 18. OPEN IDEO 19. DIY - Development Impact & you 	<p>research</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RECESSION DESIGN 2. POP MACHINA 3. MAKE-IT 4. REFLOW 5. DDMP 6. RE-PAIR 7. DESIGN LAB 8. TZOUMAKER 9. SUPERLOCAL 10. AMPLIFY 11. Cucina Leggera 12. OPEN.WORK. NET 13. Fabcity

Table 1: Case studies list

4.2 Impact assessment and sustainable re-design

The research focuses on the analysis of three tools of sustainable design: software for LCA with its quantitative tools, Eco Strategy Wheel as qualitative tool, and the Circular Design Guide¹ from Ellen MacArthur and IDEO.

The methodology Life Cycle Assessment, has been used by big companies for the first time during the '70 with the intention to control the entire supply chain and reduce the economic risks coming from raw material and energy supply.

Since that methodology has been systematized with ISO normation, specific softwares and databases have been developed to collect LCA data and assist the users in the calculation of the environment impact.

Those improvements were fundamental to get transparency of the data and so allow comparison between different product-service systems. LCA is today necessary to get most of the product-service certification.

On the other side the rise of derived methodology like the social-LCA, demontred one of the limits of this methodology and the continuous need of updated approach to follow the sustainability evolution.

Although the LCA methodology and procedure are easily understood by designers in the product-service area, but it has been found that in most cases these same designers are unable to actually develop a complete LCA analysis due to the long time required and the costs associated with the purchase of software licenses or the costs of the necessary consultancy (Vogtländer, 2010).

This leads design studios (mainly industrial and architectural / engineering design) not to use this tool and to prefer qualitative tools.

It noted a reduction in the possibilities of disseminating and validating this tool in diversified contexts, which could lead to implementations and improvements.

For the qualitative assessment, the most widespread one for the design of product-service systems is the Eco Strategy Wheel (Brezet, vanHemel, 1997). This tool allows designers to easily manage the product-service system, thanks to a total view of the phases of the life cycle and the strategies related to each of these. Despite its simplicity, it is effective in allowing the identification of critical issues and project opportunities, as well as in their communication.

The advantage lies in being able to compare different design solutions, as well as verify the improvements given by the re-design of the existing product-service.

Moreover the Circular Design Guide, is a result of Ellen MacArthur Foundation and IDEO collaboration. As they declare with this guide they don't want to give answers to users but: *helps you reframe your mindset, ask the right questions, take on projects, and start exploring the extraordinary possibilities.*

With the approach of Design thinking and Learning by doing they have lined up a number of activities to help you understand, define, make, and release circular innovations.

Starting from these considerations, during the workshop the students were asked to use the Smart Material Choices and Product Journey Templates from the Circular Design Guide, then the app Idemat and the Eco-strategy Wheel.

In general the students found the Circular Design Guide helpful to keep together the information about life-cycle during the all course.

Therefore the Idemat App was appreciated by the participants, but in most cases were observed difficulty in the use of the app, furthermore the knowledge needed to interpret the results discouraged the students.

By the way, the application of LCA for univertaries research projects in the product-service design field, confirm a good potential for improving design product, comparison of materials and suppliers, (TRAVEL, REVYTA projects) but shows lack in evaluating services systems and their social aspects (DOMO4MUB, DAPHNE projects).

¹ <https://www.circulardesignguide.com/>

In the end we can say that the application of LCA in DIY context was a surprising process for non-expert, but at the same time too approximative for selection of data, specially in case of second hand materials.

In conclusion emerged the need to have different dedicated databases, in order to develop specific items and ensure accessibility to different work categories. And the need tools for different targets. From here the assumption for the development of a phone.

4.3 Sustainability for all: the method of Easy LCA

The definition of the simplified Life Cycle Assessment methodology is the result of collaboration with Professor Joost G. Vogtländer of Delft University of Technology, Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering, founder of IDEMAT app and database, and Marco Capellini founder of database MATREC Sustainable Materials & Trends.

The goal of the Easy LCA is to increase the green skills of non-expert designers. The focus was therefore placed on the strategy to guide the users of the phone app to understand the processes that are upstream and downstream of the realization of their products, in order to make him confident with the complexity of the production systems. As background there is the dissemination of the Life Cycle Thinking approach.

It is noted that the definition of the Easy LCA methodology went hand in hand with the definition of the app structure.

The app is structured in four main sections, three of which are dedicated to learning: Assess, Compensate, Improve and a Discover section dedicated to the creation of the virtual and real community.

Figure 2: LCA simplification scheme

From a conceptual point of view, the four phases of the LCA analysis have been schematized through the interface of the app in three learning sections in the following way (Figure 2): in the first section Assess correspond to the Scope and Goal Definition, Inventory (LCI) and the Life Cycle Inventory Assessment (LCIA); the second and the third sections are dedicated to the Interpretation phase of the LCA, giving the user the opportunity to remedy the impact generated by suggesting sustainable behaviors like offsetting process (section 2), or by suggesting Life Cycle Design strategies through online training courses and tutorials (section 3). In both cases, the user is led to interact with the community and therefore to strengthen a local network (section 4).

The section *Assess* is the most complex and gives the originality to the project. Here the user is guided in the realization of his inventory (Figure 3). First of all it asks the user if he will use new materials, so consult the dedicated materials DB derived by Idemat; or if he has the intention to use second hand materials, and so is given to him the opportunity to consult the *Market* section of the app, where there are offer of materials made by other users.

During the consultation the users could select and drag in his basket the items he needed for his project, name it and add content like draws or pictures.

In the second step it will be asked to enter the quantity relating to the selected items.

Then the user is faced with the problem of having waste materials and choosing the end-of-life for them, as well as the end-of-life of the product itself. Those choices and their impacts are included in the total calculation of the impact, and help the user to become aware of the whole consequences of his design choices, introducing him to a systemic approach.

Figure 3: Medium wireframe from section Asses

The interpretation phase is where normally strategic hypotheses are made to improve and reduce the impacts. In this case the reflexive phase where the actions to reach sustainability are chosen, are delegated to two sections.

In the section *Compensate* the user is put in the position to compare the impact generated by his project with the impact of action that he can avoid or take in order to compensate for the environmental impact of his project. This works like the offsetting strategy adopted nowadays by companies.

By the way, in the section *Improve* is proposed a different strategy based on the redesign of the product. In this section the user found multimedia content like online classes, case studies, or on site workshops dedicated to sustainable design, that gives the user the opportunity to understand and apply the basic concepts to reduce the impact of his project.

Moreover, from a practical point of view, the Easy LCA methodology is based on the work made on the Idemat database. The work was carried out on the research tables of Idemat Excel (available on www.ecocostvalue.com) with information regarding the impacts due to the extraction and processing of materials, as well as the impacts due to the production and disposal processes (EoL).

It was considered appropriate to simplify this database to make it dedicated for the self-production sector. A first pre-selection of the relevant items for the context of application was then made, then their values were observed on the basis of the selected impact categories, namely Carbon Footprint and Eco-cost. Of

these, the first was chosen because it is the most used, the second instead because it monetises the value making it more easily understandable to non-employees.

From the observation of these values it was possible to create a scale of values to insert these into ranges from which to extrapolate a further visual example that will then be used in the app interface and thanks to which the user can contextualize that obtained value.

4.4 The app: MAKE IT DIFFERENT

The approach used to develop the app phone came from Cradle to Cradle Design, to build the learning process for the users as explained above, then Service Design, User Experience Design and the Engagement Design approach were applied to define the structure and the storytelling.

In particular the tools applied are: Benchmarking, Swot analysis, Context matrix, Brief, Info architecture, Stakeholder map, Networking Map, Personas, User journey, Service blueprint and a medium wireframe for the mockup generated with Adobe XD.

The output of the research is a collaborative App mobile name *Make It Different*, where users arrive to get information and improve their expertise, but at the same time they could generate new content for the other users. The most valid example comes from Personas (3) *The innovative craftsman*, she can use the app to assess the impact of her products and look for collaboration, but she can even propose tutorials about her work and knowledge, like how to get products lasting with special treatment.

For the definition of the project and the assessment of feasibility, the UI / UX Design tools were applied. The following categories have been identified as the stakeholders of the project: MPI of the construction and building materials sector, multinationals of the large distribution of semi-finished products for construction, freelancers and artisans related to the construction sector, related trade associations, cultural associations and social workers working in crafts, municipalities, research institutes, databases of materials, students and in general creative figures.

They were then inserted in a Matrix to evaluate both their level of influence and interest in the project, and finally through a mapping of the networking it was possible to define the relationships already existing between them and those relationships to be built or strengthened for the purposes of the project (Figure 4).

From the analysis using the Stakeholder Matrix and Networking Map tools, it emerged that among most of them, despite belonging to the same sector or neighboring sectors, there are no direct relationships that guarantee a communication channel for the exchange of skills or materials from which to bring out new market opportunities.

The categories of stakeholders identified were subsequently divided according to the role played within the project. It was possible to proceed with the Personas tool, identify the archetype, so typical user profiles that describe the role of the category within the project. And then using the User Journey tool for each of these profiles it was possible to prefigure the way to use the service for each archetype and then establish the construction of the interface.

In particular, were outlined four Personas: *The Fixer* that sensible to sustainability want to do something in his own small, he is looking for sustainable material and tips; *The Ambitious Creative* she want to improve manual skills, and she is looking for classes and collaborations; *The Innovative Craftsman* want to renovate her job through the sustainability channel, she want to find a community to share her knowledge and values; *The Smart Manager* want to be part of a local sustainable network.

Figure 4: Networking map and Personas archetypes

To closely describe those profiles, a form has been created in which are identified the objectives and aspirations, the list of obstacles that prevent the archetype from achieving the objectives, as well as parameter relevant for the project like the scale for the levels of knowledge and a scale for the level of engagement on the two topics of the platform: Eco-consciousness and DIY-consciousness.

The User Journey tool is used to describe the interaction between the user and the service, through a synthetic representation of all phases of the experience and the description of all actions (or activities) phase by phase.

APP CONCEPT

“Collect the STONES to create your SKILLS TOTEM and become a GREEN GURU of the community”

Figure 5: Concept of the user journey through the four principle sections of the app, with their own stone win for each action taken in that section , and consequent totem conformation.

From here it has been possible to design and make corrections on the blueprint of the app service. Moreover it has been possible to outline the gamification that creates the engagement.

The users are guided through the sections of the App to gain points and green skills, with a storytelling that embodies them in a jungle of knowledge, where building a personal totem that shows their growth, they move from initiates level to the level of guru of sustainability (Figure 5).

The totem is a symbolic object, in this case caratherazid the profile of the user and allowed him to present himself to the community for his actions and knowledge in the section of *Social Wall*. Here arrives the social proof where users meet each other, and start collaboration by just sharing materials or offering their know-how and freetime (Figure 6).

User involvement was built according to four key points: personalization, participation, rewarding, social proof (Viola, 2020). The MOAR scheme was followed based on the creation of motivation, opportunity, action and result; these four put together in a row give life to a circular process that tends to feed itself thanks to the creation of new involvement.

Furthermore, to be more effective, the fun component was used. Various paths have therefore been designed that guarantee rewarding experiences but with different levels of involvement. Actions with a different level of involvement which correspond to a feedback system based on scores and levels. All this therefore passes through the principles of rewarding and social proof that push users to generate collaborations between them through which to generate unique experiences for users and therefore memories that will feed the retrospective engagement phase.

APP CONCEPT

Figure 6: Wireframe Profile section and Totem Social Wall

In this specific case, the user is intercepted on the one hand with the curiosity to discover the environmental impact of the products, as in the fast-impact platforms related to lifestyle but the app offer a service on a specific field; on the other hand, in order to give consistency to his sustainable behaviors, the app offer service not just to give a result but to improve the own expertise to get that result. It generates interest in the user thanks to the opportunities to improve his skills and be part of a network.

A relevant goal of the App has been to create a solid community thanks to the involvement of different stakeholders, from production companies to craftsmen. Those together with the users are able to generate material and immaterials contents, and share it first in the virtual and then in real world, in order to give strength to the community and move it from the web to the real territory.

As a consequence it is planned to achieve a circular and sustainable valorization of the territory.

5 Conclusion: limits and opportunities

The main limitation for the project is therefore the lack of data relating to semi-finished products, in fact it is difficult for non-expert users to reconstruct their inventory starting from raw materials. Consequently, it is noticed the need to generate new kinds of databases where the information are packed in the way to be received from a different target.

In conclusion, the project highlights the presence of opportunities for sustainable growth at the grassroots level. Here the prosumers, like DIY people and makers, with the right tools could play a relevant role in the amplification of sustainable thinking.

In the same way, the project envisages a new scenario of application of the LCA methodology in new and informal contexts, in order to stimulate technicians to investigate the implementation of the methodology out of the box.

One possible role of designers is to facilitate the on-going transition by creating conditions for people to use creativity and innovate at the local scale and that of design researchers is to provide designers with a theoretical ground by understanding the environment in which collaborative services are created, developed and replicated and supporting them with appropriate methodologies (Manzini, 2015).

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